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SOCIALLY RESPONSIVE DESIGN - OPEN AND PARTICIPATORY DESIGN LED SOCIAL INNOVATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the links between crime, design and innovation. It is written in two sections. The first discusses ideas about the ‘dark side of creativity’ a concept that considers the shared aptitudes of criminal and designers. It explains how designers might use this similarity to help them to design against crime, and introduces the user and abuser focused methodology of the Design Against Crime Research Centre in London that addresses social issues via participatory and collaborative design activities described as ‘socially responsive design’. The second looks at the ‘open innovation’ approach, originally explained by Chesborough (2003), as it is applied within the process of research led socially responsive design. The paper considers the process of the resulting social impact to be desirable, optimal and sustainable in economic and non-economic terms.

Keywords: Crime, Social Innovation, Open Innovation.

WHAT DO CRIMINALS AND DESIGNERS HAVE IN COMMON?

One of the reasons designers may be well placed to engage in crime prevention is that effective designers appear to have a lot in common with effective criminals. These commonalities are apparent in qualities linked to ‘effectuation and contingency’ (Sarasvathy, 2003) including:

- perceptions of risk/opportunity -i.e. probability of harm vs. probability of benefit
- preparedness to embrace and emulate ‘outliers’ to cause or exploit ‘change’
- exploitation of networks

Also, the ability to respond creatively to and/or manipulate:

- understanding of ‘real world’ context(s)
- understanding of emotions (fraud/experiential/emotive design)
- understanding of human behaviours
- understanding of ‘drivers’/ ‘motivations’ in relation to ‘systems’ of (ab)use

PERCEPTIONS OF RISK/OPPORTUNITY -I.E.

PROBABILITY OF HARM VS PROBABILITY OF BENEFIT

The ‘transgression’ necessary for an individual to view a situation that may benefit them as an ‘opportunity’ rather than a ‘risk’ despite the potential for a negative impact or outcome (‘harm’ that could come to them or others as a result of exploiting the situation) is also observed by Anthony Julius (2002) to be common to both creatives and criminals. Julius considers the manner in which these individuals assume that they are ‘luckier’ (rather than simply less risk averse) than others. Such convictions appear to help creatives (and criminals who believe that they can ‘pull off’ the crime) go forward and try to succeed at their self-appointed tasks.

Explanations of an increased capacity for risk taking may be linked to what has been described as “sideways thinking” (Gamman and Hughes, 2003, Gamman and Thorpe 2010a) a perspective that reframes ‘risks’ as ‘opportunities’ in a similar way to that by which designers reframe, as Schön (1983) describes, ‘challenges’ or ‘problems’ as ‘opportunities’ for design intervention linked to ‘design thinking’ (Tim Brown 2009). Both approaches demonstrate a heightened ability to scan, spot, and reframe a scenario that most perceive as a ‘problem’ for exploitation as an ‘opportunity’.

In practice, these ‘opportunist’ approaches appear consistent with the ability of heightened visual perception and recognition, a quality associated with those who have dyslexia (Raein 2003).

Perhaps it is no coincidence then that ‘creatives’ and ‘criminals’ are reported to display higher levels of dyslexia than other groups (Gamman and Thorpe 2010b). For example, Levan Lumb (2005) writes how within the population of the United Kingdom around 4% of people are severely dyslexic and a further 6% have mild to moderate dyslexia. Within the UK’s prison population 80% of prisoners have poor writing skills, 50% have reading difficulties and 65% have trouble with numeracy.

According to the UK Higher Education Statistics Agency figures, 1.97% of all undergraduate students are dyslexic. However, of those studying course areas described as ‘Creative Arts and Design’, 5.59% are reported to be dyslexic. Thus, while a student in higher education is five times less likely to be dyslexic than a member of the broader population, a student of ‘Creative Arts and Design’ is only twice less likely to be dyslexic. Put another way, if you are dyslexic and in higher education, you are most likely to be studying ‘creative arts and design’.

While these statistics do not ‘prove’ a link between dyslexia and ‘criminality’ nor dyslexia and ‘creativity’, they do indicate that ‘criminal’ and ‘creative’ populations have higher incidence of dyslexia and therefore may share the attributes afforded to dyslexics. In addition to lower than average reading and numeracy skills these groups demonstrate a shared emphasis/dependence on visual learning styles, which in practice develop and display regard for “positive deviance” (Brown and Wyatt 2010).

***PREPAREDNESS TO EMBRACE AND EMULATE
‘OUTLIERS’ TO CAUSE OR EXPLOIT ‘CHANGE’***

Positive Deviance (Stermin, 2000), as an approach, looks for solutions among individuals and groups in the community who are doing ‘well’. By considering these ‘outliers’ (Gladwell 2009), focusing on the edges, the places where ‘extreme’ people live differently or think differently, and consume differently. Positive deviance seeks to identify strategies for creating outcomes that are ‘desirable’, either by copying, or adapting the observed

behaviour in a new context toward a desirable outcome. The validity of this approach within social innovation, and more latterly design led social innovation, is evidenced by many case studies documented by, amongst others, the Positive Deviance Initiative and also less predictably by the DESIS Network¹ who appear to follow a version of the ‘positive deviance process’ (Pascale, Sternin, & Sternin, 2010) in their work and collection and collation of case studies. The approach is articulated in relation to the social innovation and design context by social innovators such as Pascale, Sternin and Sternin (2010) and ‘design thinkers’ such as Tim Brown. Practice of a ‘positive deviance’ approach amongst criminals is evidenced by the spread of crime types, and therefore criminal modus operandi, in response to sociological, cultural or situational (or other contextual) changes effecting the population e.g. the introduction of what Ron Clarke et al (2000) have defined as ‘criminogenic’ objects, systems or services. Positive deviance may also have some bearing on the incidence of repeat offending and criminal progression associated with ‘first offenders’. When are imprisoned alongside more experienced felons first offenders learn from them. Despite this, knowledge exchange takes place in the penal system, a context perceived by most to be evidence of an undesirable outcome - first offenders still appear to regard acquiring this knowledge as an opportunity. This is where the criminal account of positive deviance aligns criminals with entrepreneurs, linked to the ‘centrality of contingency’ to entrepreneurship described by Sarasvathy (2003) i.e. making the most of those resources that are available within the observed time and context. It is also where we challenge the role of ‘luck’ within opportunism (criminal or otherwise) as it is replaced by an active understanding of how to ‘leverage contingency’. These young offenders exhibit what Jenny Kaufman Singer (2010) discusses as ‘creativity in confinement’ by exercising their positive deviance by leveraging the contingency of meeting with ‘expert outsiders’ - the experienced felons within the prison - to learn from their experiences and MO’s.

¹See: www.positivedeviance.org/about_pd/case_studies.html and www.desis-network.org

Lester and Piore (2004) have developed a similar account that discusses the way artists and fashion designers are able to start different 'conversations' that are documented (Oakley et al, 2008) as generating creativity and innovation. This account of innovative discourse may go some way towards addressing the gaps in understanding how creatives work.

The creativity of the criminal class is less acknowledged (with the exception of gangster and crime fictions that abound in popular culture) even though real criminals often generate significant innovation as well as income. Indeed, in some instances, criminals may be considered as equipped experts (Ekblom and Tilley 2000), extreme or malevolent innovators (Cropley 2010) or lead (ab)users (Von Hippel 2005).

However, within certain case studies there is ambiguity as to whether the behaviour identified can easily be defined as either 'criminal' or 'creative'. The account of the professional lock breaker, Marc Weber Tobias (2009) who has dedicated his life to cracking physical security systems, is a good example. This lock breaker has no record for criminal acts and so we can find no evidence he is in anyway a criminal. Instead, according to Wired magazine (2009) he 'thinks of himself as a humble public servant' who is, 'protecting consumers by exposing locks, safes, and security systems that aren't actually locked, safe, or secure.' For some with vested interests, this man is not just exposing problems, they say, 'he is the problem', and in our view has much in common with the prankster or deconstructive artist. Tobias may do it for fun, and he may serve the public of legitimate users who need to know when their faith in their security is ill founded. However, those with criminal intentions may misuse his website that streams videos of how to break into things. Tobias has no problem with the law because he can enjoy breaking locks, experiencing 'criminal' transgression, without actually committing a crime.

Moreover, of course, we should be aware of this difference between designers and criminals too - that criminals are more likely to break the law because of their practices! However, there are other, unlegislated, differences. One of the most significant we observe is that the designer or artist

usually has a collective account about the function of their work, or has a sense of the higher purpose of its meaning. They also find innovative ways of making social comment and artistic meanings as well as generating capital to earn a legitimate living. Often the responsiveness of designers and artists is also linked to some sense of social accountability or egalitarianism, particularly in the context of design led social innovation, which we discuss further in the second half of this paper. So when we say we observe 'creativity' or 'innovative capacity' in the behaviour of criminals, we must specify that we are referring primarily to what Ekblom and Tilley (2000) call 'resourceful offenders', that is, the behaviour of shoplifters, bank robbers, confidence tricksters, identity fraud crews, burglars and thieves who make money from their 'practice' linked to opportunistic, perhaps even entrepreneurial, activities and ideas. We however, exclude from our account criminals whose activities are linked to mindless vandalism, violence, and murder.

We also recognize that professional burglars and shoplifters do not usually aim to make creative statements, in the way that designers typically enjoy. Nor, do criminals typically apply empathic methods to positive ends linked to serving the needs of others - their 'clients' - preferring to apply empathy to predict a response or behaviour in order that they might manipulate it for their own personal gain, ignoring the needs of others - their 'victims'. Similarly, although both criminals and designers review design weaknesses or problems, criminals do so primarily to outwit security systems or victimise users, whilst designers typically apply this positive deviance and transgressive opportunism to the improvement of products, systems or services. In light of the above, when setting up the Design Against Crime Research Centre (DACRC), which first emerged at Central Saint Martins (CSM) as a 'design initiative' in 1999, the possibility that designers might have an aptitude for 'thinking thief' was eagerly anticipated. Thirteen years later this aptitude is evidenced by designers' contributions to DACRC outputs, which have won awards for innovation² and been well cited and acknowledged as

² See: The Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) currently cites DACRC's projects as exemplars of impact in research. www.ahrc.ac.uk/About/Publications/.../DAC%20Brochure.pdf. For

exemplars and an inspiration to others in the field. All DACRC activities have aimed at inspiring other designers to have a go at ‘thinking thief’, to feed positive deviance within the community of design research and practice. To encourage them to design against crime, without losing sight of the typical/legitimate ‘user’ i.e. usually the taxpaying majority of the population!

HOW EMBRACING CRIME CAN BENEFIT DESIGNERS

The societal benefits of harnessing the abilities and aptitudes of designers to tackle crime are self-evident and include economic, emotional, situational and ecological justifications that have been discussed at length elsewhere (Gamman and Thorpe 2009). What is less obvious is the benefit afforded designers in seeking to design against crime. As described above effective designers, like effective criminals, typically exhibit positive deviance; considering the actions and strategies of ‘outliers’ for what they may contribute to innovation within their own practice. Whilst positive deviance is a shared attribute, when the designer considers the ‘outliers’ within the criminal community they are amplifying the effect; considering the ‘outliers’ of the ‘outliers’, ‘doubling the difference’ experienced and the potential for unpredicted innovation. This is the kind of ethnographic reach that is required if designers are to keep pace with the changing and evolving practices of the ‘adaptive criminal’ (Ekblom 1997). It is also this kind of trans-disciplinary understanding that affords innovative opportunity within design practice. Put another way, when a designer engages with design against crime they do not simply apply the understandings and attributes of their own discipline but engage with those of the adaptive criminal, including their aptitude for effectuation and contingency. This process of ‘thinking thief’ can afford more than insights into how best to design against crime. Insights gained relating to effectuation and contingency are of particular use to designers working within complex and dynamic contexts. Also

example, the Australian Designing Out Crime Research Centre (2007) cites DACRC’s work at Central Saint Martins as a significant influence <http://www.designingoutcrime.com.au/research-centre/> DACRC’s user and abuser centered approach has been documented and disseminated in several design resources and numerous academic papers, which may be familiar thanks to the efforts of the UK’s Design Council.

of benefit to those considering complex or ‘wicked’ design scenarios (Buchanan 1992), is the necessity that resides within design against crime practice to understand and consider the systems of (ab)use i.e. the attitudes, attributes and actions that comprise the modus operandi of, and interrelations between, both desirable, legitimate users and potentially undesirable miss-users and abusers (criminals). This necessary minimum requirement to consider and address multiple and conflicting agendas in relation to the design of objects, systems and services provides good grounding for those designers seeking to address further social design scenarios

HOW TO COMBINE THE INSIGHTS AND APPROACHES OF USERS AND ABUSERS WITHIN THE DESIGN PROCESS.

Core to DACRC’s work within design, education and industry, has been the identification and visualisation of criminal perpetrator techniques, to encourage designers not just to ‘think thief’, but also to help them understand in practical terms how criminals get away with crimes within prescribed contexts. This is achieved by introducing both qualitative and quantitative research into the design process.

In terms of qualitative research, DACRC draws upon the thieves’ perspective. DACRC engages with the idea of ‘thinking thief’ (Ekblom, 1997) but goes further, consulting - and where possible involving - offenders, victims and the police within the research. The methods utilised to do this include: focus groups, such as those DACRC undertook on bike theft linked to Brighton Probation services in 2008, Oral history, such as the work undertaken by Gamman with the shoplifter Shirley Pitts between 1982-1992, role-play such as ‘body storming’ and ‘shadowing’ techniques introduced to the Karrysafe project linked to the services of self defense trainer Sev McArty 2002. Whilst shadowing is obviously difficult and contentious from an ethical perspective in relation to crime, raising issues of complicity and entrapment, re-enactment has been used to similar effect. For example, Martin Gill (2007) has helped connect theory to practice by taking shop thieves back to the scene of their offences and asking them to talk through their thinking whilst re-enacting offences in their original context. This work was

pivotal in identifying six key decision points that must crucially be understood if shoplifting is to be addressed by design. A further method commonly applied within our projects to access and share knowledge and identify key research questions and insights involves our researchers in acts of ‘immersion’ within relevant communities and activities - such as cycling communities and activities linked to the bikeoff project (Thorpe et al 2010). These research activities generate a visual response, defining the insights gained, including criminal MO’s. The act of visualising insights corroborates understanding and facilitates effective knowledge exchange.

Thus, DACRC has formalised the process of ‘thinking thief’ by ensuring visual material about what thieves do - theft MO’s - is understood clearly in the initial stages of research and iteratively revisited at every stage of the design process.

SO MUCH FOR ATTENDING TO CONCERNS OF THE ABUSER (CRIMINAL), WHAT OF THE USER?

Whilst our DAC process requires designers to ‘think thief’, we have learned from experience of our own practice-led approach, as well as from the failure of design models either based on theoretical speculation (See Life Cycle Model UK Design Council, 2003) or police experience (which is based upon sometimes very heavy handed design interventions) to crucially ‘think user’ first. Ultimately, it is essential to prioritise ‘thinking user’ over ‘thinking

use. If such interventions fail the user they will ultimately not be used and thus fail to deliver the impact they seek. Therefore, the objects, systems and services we design are easy to use, and easy on the eye as well as resistant to abuse. Such an approach helps us to avoid creating objects and environments that appear ‘paranoid’ (Gamman and Thorpe, 2007) or contribute to what has been called a ‘fortress society’ (Gamman and Pascoe 2005) So, at the outset, we know we wish to avoid design proposals that focus on deterring the abuser at the expense of embracing the user, or lead us to strategies that promote civil security at the expense of civil rights.

We have described in detail the nine stages of our design process at length in other publications (Gamman and Thorpe 2010). The process is illustrated in the diagram below. The nine-stage process can be summarised more broadly as ‘scope and consult’; ‘research and create’; ‘create and consult’; ‘create and test’. Significantly, there are two ‘tracks’ to our process. The first ‘track’, shown in the diagram, as a blue arrow is practice led research. We are typically most interested in those research insights that are of value to design practitioners in their attempts to appropriately and effectively serve the needs of users. The second ‘track’ is that of research led practice. Within this ‘track’, our design teams iteratively seek to apply the research insights to prototype design proposals that can be used by researchers within the action

Figure 1 Twin Track Model of the Iterative Design Process

thief’ when designing products, systems and services intended to reduce crime as a consequence of their

research process.

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The aim of this process of iterative visualization and prototyping is to help us check the propriety and value of research insights gained and how they might best inform the practice of designers. For example, communication designs or product or service prototypes may be iteratively tested and reviewed by the communities they aim to serve. We discuss the benefits of this process in the second half of this paper.

After twelve years practice of design against crime, DACRC has developed this open action research model to try to articulate the means by which we have been able to adapt our research and design responses to keep step with the adaptive criminal. What may be less clear from the dissemination of our research within a 'crime' focused account, is that the models of the design process we have generated to address crime problems, are also transferable to address other social issues and scenarios. This is why we talk about this work as "socially responsive design," defined as "design that takes as its primary driver social issues, its main consideration social impact and its main objective social change" (Gamman and Thorpe 2006). We have used the DACRC design research model to brief national master classes (Sustain our nation 2009) and competitions (RSA Design Directed Projects) linked to broader social themes including climate change, ageing, alternative finance and health. Additionally the models have proven useful to both our own practice and that of private agencies delivering design led strategies for social innovation beyond crime issues, linked to ageing and health.

THE IMPACT OF 'OPEN INNOVATION' ON EFFECTUATION AND CONTINGENCY IN SOCIALLY RESPONSIVE DESIGN

The 'open innovation' model (Chesbrough, 2006), when applied to the research process (as well as the design process within our twin track model) can describe the way DACRC researchers, within projects such as Bikeoff, openly share research and exchange knowledge with a variety of stakeholders within an 'open' action research process (Thorpe et al 2009). We argue that this 'open' process optimizes impact of research and best promotes effectiveness of design outputs that respond to that research.

We have found this approach useful because by consulting with many groups, as our research emerges, we have been able to target research more effectively by understanding what knowledge and resource gaps exist that might be addressed by research and design.

Significantly, such an approach requires research to be shared in a language that is accessible to a diverse range of disciplines and communities. Because we want our stakeholders and dutyholders (those who have a duty of care in relation to the social issue being addressed) to shape our research, we visualise information we wish to share using creative strategies including, illustration, animation, video, 3d prototypes and role-playing³ This process of design-led visualisation facilitates and democratizes knowledge exchange between different disciplines and 'communities of knowledge and practice' to help co-creation of research questions and design briefs.

Figure 2 Chesbrough's model of open innovation, 2003.

Consequently, what this open innovation research process offers to researchers, as Thorpe et al (2009) identified, is "an ability to engage multiple disciplines (both inside and outside design) and multiple stakeholders, in tackling complex design scenarios. It achieves this by sharing knowledge and experience. It also makes research available in accessible forms enabling a diversity of responses necessary to address the multitude of contexts that exist."

Our experience of delivering DAC as well as SRvD has found that such 'open' processes not only enrich the research but also create many opportunities for new

³ See: www.inthebag.org.uk, Know the enemy Bicycle film festival Cochrane and Barbican events and body storming with Sev Necati available at: www.designaginstcrime.com

types of research dissemination and exploitation, linked to open knowledge exchange with other individuals and organisations effected by, or interested in, the research. In fact, when applied to the research process Chesbrough’s model of ‘open’ innovation leads to more, and more unpredicted, outputs compared to ‘closed’ or traditional research processes. For example, the model of ‘open research innovation’ delivered within Bikeoff’s application of the twin track design methodology enabled interdisciplinary research and the inclusion of diverse stakeholder knowledge and practice, which maximised research outputs and impact. The AHRC funded Bikeoff project ended up producing over 100 ‘emergent’ outputs in addition to the 15 predicted outputs we said we would achieve at the outset (see

<http://www.bikeoff.org/tags/bikeoff-outputs>). This surprising excess of outputs was linked to the fact that as knowledge was exchanged and insight shared it was applied within the practices of many of those exposed to the research - both those that were core to the project and those that were less intensely involved. Beneficiaries of the research included private, public and third sector groups who applied the research outputs (sometimes in collaboration with the core research team and sometimes not) to deliver positive economic outcomes - including sales of new products designed as a result of the research, and social outcomes (including changes in cyclists behaviors and reductions in cycle theft). Figures 3 and 4 illustrate this process.

Figure 3 Gamman and Thorpe Model of open research innovation showing ‘open’ interdisciplinary working leading to unexpected outputs, 2009. After Chesbrough 2003.

Figure 4 Gamman and Thorpe Model of closed research innovation showing ‘closed’ multidisciplinary working leading to predicted outputs. After Chesbrough 2003.

Visualisation and the design of creative dissemination strategies were essential to optimisation of knowledge exchange, interdisciplinary research synthesis, and ultimately the application of the research outputs to practice. A variety of approaches were used to aid research dissemination. Prototypes and product exemplars were exhibited, films and animations were created and curated and screened to visualize different aspects of the research. These design led creative research dissemination strategies aided communication and knowledge transfer between disciplines and stakeholders - enjoyment drove involvement - facilitating greater creative contribution and collaboration. This open engagement also helped ensure that research questions stayed close to the interests and needs of potential beneficiaries of the research, and because much of the research was collaboratively realized with stakeholders it was easily and readily applied by them.

SOCIALLY RESPONSIVE DESIGN AS A 'MORE THAN' MODEL OF RESEARCH AND DESIGN

The open innovation approach to research, in our view, is capable of generating 'social capital' of particular value to the knowledge economies of the twenty first century. This is because the knowledge exchange implicit in open innovation incentivises engagement of individuals and groups within the research process, creating 'communities of interest and practice' and 'knowledge networks', the like of which have been recognized to foster economic, social and cultural innovation outlined by Leadbeater and Medway (2008). Typically drivers for innovation in design have been market led. That is, the exploitation of creativity has been towards creation of products aimed at the generation of economic capital via 'the market'. Social enterprises are described as 'more than profit' enterprises rather than 'not for profit' enterprises, so as to describe the manner in which such businesses embrace economic benefit. Similarly as a way of sustaining social benefit, so socially responsive research and design may be considered to be 'more than market led and user centred' in that it does not shun the economic benefits of market engagement nor user centred considerations of desirability, but

rather seeks to harness them toward attainment of sustainable and desirable social impact. DACRC's seven year Bikeoff project sought to apply design research and practice to increase cycle use by reducing cycle theft. The project achieved this and more and successfully 'exploited creativity' in two distinct ways, linked to DARC's twin track model of design focused open action research. Firstly, through the creation of products that have been licensed to industry and introduced to the market and constitute economic innovation⁴. These products also build 'operational capacity' amongst those seeking to promote cycling via provision of secure cycling infrastructure or via cycle theft prevention. This increase in operational capacity constitutes social innovation in that it promotes cycling by deterring cycle theft. Secondly, project effectuation is linked to the development and open dissemination of 'knowledge made accessible', toolkits, design resources and guidance that contributes to 'innovative capacity' i.e. the ability of others to exploit/apply research findings within their own practice and context. In the case of Bikeoff, open access resources were made available on the Bikeoff.org website that could help practitioners to deliver their own designed solutions or crime prevention interventions.⁵ Realization of innovative capacity, of course, also helps develop 'operational capacity'. In the instance of Bikeoff, for the providers of secure cycling infrastructure and cycle theft prevention practitioners. Thus the 'market' for our 'products' (research 'outputs' as well as design) was not limited to commerce or even narrow academic or crime prevention communities but spanned a broader range of beneficiaries. Such an approach is at the heart of all our design and research projects and is obviously transferable. Bikeoff may have wanted to help cyclists improve their security in order to encourage more cycling, but like any project with a change agenda, we sought to maximise the reach and impact

⁴ See M stand available at: <http://www.designagainstcrime.com/projects/camden-stands/>

⁵ See: Plantlock Available at: <http://www.frontyardcompany.co.uk/> and Cyclehoop Available at: <http://www.cyclehoop.com/> CSEP.

of the research. We feel the Open Innovation model when linked to the action research process helped us more effectively meet that objective, and that others engaging with social innovation as well as socially responsive design projects should review it for similar purpose.

Additionally, the model appears to have a contribution to make in address to the common causes of failure within the traditional economic model of the innovation process in most organisations (O'Sullivan 2002). For as we have explained elsewhere (Thorpe 2009) by openly involving the community of interest within the process it helps reduce possibilities for such failure to occur, and can enable those engaging in socially responsive design projects to understand how best to build effectuation into the design process, and weather change by embracing contingency in their actions.

The literature about "effectuation" explains how entrepreneurs in the business realm have found ways to better manage risk. Sarasvathy, (2003) discusses the decision making principles that successful entrepreneurs draw upon when faced with situations of uncertainty. She located five techniques of non-predictive control that she suggests leads to effectuation. These include:

The 'patchwork quilt principle'. This is a principle of means-driven (as opposed to goal-driven) action. The emphasis here is on creating something new with existing means rather than discovering new ways to achieve given goals.

The 'affordable loss principle'. This principle prescribes committing in advance to what one is willing to lose rather than investing in calculations about expected returns to the project.

The 'bird-in-hand principle'. This principle involves negotiating with any, and all stakeholders who are willing to make actual commitments to the project, without worrying about opportunity costs, or carrying out elaborate competitive analyses.

Furthermore, who comes on board determines the goals of the enterprise. Not vice versa.

The 'lemonade principle'. This principle suggests acknowledging and appropriating contingency by leveraging surprises rather than trying to avoid them, overcome them, or adapt to them.

The pilot-in-the-plane principle. This principle urges relying on and working with human agency as the prime driver of opportunity rather than limiting entrepreneurial efforts to exploiting exogenous factors such as technological trajectories and socio-economic trends.

Sarasvathy (2003) believes the above offer useful design principles for transforming extant environments into new futures in the face of ambiguous goals. A statement we believe well describes the delivery of socially responsive design within 'wicked' contexts.

The logic behind the account of effectuation has been explained in terms of non-predictive control and focus on human action and agency. Effectuators work to fabricate, as well as recognize and discover opportunities (Sarasvathy, Dew, Velamuri, & Venkataraman, 2004) and may do so for criminal as well as legitimate entrepreneurial purposes, with the shared aim of making money. Effectual models begin with non-predictive strategies and tend to contrast markedly with conventional management practices. The account of effectuation offers a logic that rearranges traditional relationships and understandings, and instead offers of a comprehensive alternate frame for tackling entrepreneurial problems. Put simply, this comes about by (a) finding ways to transform who the entrepreneur is, what she knows and whom she knows into new ventures and markets and (b) finding ways for entrepreneurs to create new networks of self-selected stakeholders. Successful entrepreneurs and/or criminal opportunists instinctively know how to do this.

In our experience of delivering socially responsive design via an open action research process we have found that many of the principles of effectuation described above are implicit in the process. We have also found that this process optimises desirable outputs and outcomes from research, a characteristic that we feel should be made clear, rather than understood via the activities of businessmen or criminals. Such processes are very useful to the life or death of projects that seek to serve our communities and should not be ignored in times of austerity, or at a time when the requirement for research impact is a key target of many different types of funders. Our conclusion in

reviewing this matter in light of the experiences of the Design Against Crime Research Centre, who have significantly engaged with participatory and open innovation design processes, is that such processes, used to deliver sustainable research and design projects, necessarily require engagement with business or commercial understandings in order to give such projects appropriate transferability, and legacy, as well as success. It is here we believe the understanding of the opportunistic mindset - from both criminal, creative and business communities, As linked to the account of effectuation, has much to contribute to ideas about how best to reframe design objectives and processes and reform them so they can effectively serve social agendas.

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